

Demonstrating the effectiveness of combining heuristic and data-driven methods to achieve scalable and adaptive motion styles

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Figure 1: This figure illustrates the evolution of motion style transfer techniques, distinguishing between heuristic and data-driven methods. Heuristic methods, such as Etemad et al.’s (2016) perceptual features, rely on predefined rules for efficient and interpretable motion modeling. In contrast, data-driven methods, including Starke et al.’s (2022) DeepPhase, Petrovich et al.’s (2020) Transformer VAEs, and Aberman et al.’s (2020) generator frameworks, utilize neural networks to achieve adaptability and realism. Recent works, like Jang et al. (2022) and Song et al. (2024), further integrate advanced data-driven architectures to enable real-time synthesis. Our hybrid framework combines the computational efficiency of heuristic features (e.g., RBF, phase features) with the adaptability of autoencoders, addressing scalability and flexibility challenges in motion style transfer.

ABSTRACT

Motion style transfer has significantly progressed through data-driven methods, offering high-quality results but demanding extensive datasets, making them resource-intensive. In contrast, heuristic methods operate with minimal motion data but lack adaptability. This paper introduces a hybrid framework integrating specific heuristic techniques, including Radial Basis Functions (RBF) and phase features, with data-driven autoencoder models to balance efficiency and precision in motion style transfer. By leveraging the efficiency of heuristic methods and the adaptability of autoencoders, this proof-of-concept demonstrates the potential for scalable and adaptive motion styles with reduced dataset dependency. While this work focuses on combining these specific meth-

ods, the framework can be generalized and extended to incorporate more advanced techniques in future developments. Our experiments on XIA, 100Style, and SHS(Share Space) datasets validate the framework’s ability to produce high-quality, adaptive motion styles, paving the way for scalable motion adaptation in applications such as gaming, VR, and robotics.

Index Terms: Motion Style Transfer, Heuristic Methods, Data-Driven Models.

1 INTRODUCTION

The advancement of interactive applications in video games, robotics, virtual reality, and animated films has amplified the demand for realistic human motion modeling. These applications require natural and expressive animations, where motion style—defined by how actions are performed—plays a pivotal role. Motion refers to the action performed, while style defines how the action is executed (e.g., walking fast, slow, happy, or sad)[11, 13, 1]. Style enriches the realism of motion and is essential for creating engaging animations that resonate with human perception [1, 9]. Generating diverse motion styles presents signif-

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icant challenges. Traditional methods, such as manual animation or motion capture, are resource-intensive and time-consuming [4]. Data-driven approaches, leveraging extensive motion datasets, have become prominent solutions. However, these methods face two critical limitations: (1) the requirement for paired and registered motion data, where characters must perform actions in all styles, and (2) the difficulty of building comprehensive datasets encompassing all potential variations [4, 2, 14]. These dependencies on large datasets restrict the scalability of data-driven approaches and hinder their generalization to unseen scenarios.

Motion style transfer offers a promising solution by mapping input motions into various styles using existing data. This approach reduces the need to generate extensive new datasets and automates the creation of realistic motion variations, saving animators significant time and effort [2, 5]. However, despite these advantages, motion style transfer is constrained by the limited availability of motion samples and the complexity of transferring styles effectively in data-scarce scenarios.

Recent advancements in deep learning, particularly neural network models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)[7, 6] and Deep Neural Networks (DNNs)[17, 15, 8], have addressed some of these challenges. These models demonstrate efficacy in generating realistic motions with high scalability, faster runtimes, and lower memory requirements. However, their reliance on extensive training datasets remains a bottleneck, limiting their scalability and adaptability [4].

To address these challenges, we propose a hybrid framework that integrates heuristic techniques with data-driven models. Specifically, we leverage Radial Basis Functions (RBF)[3] and frequency-based analysis[16] to complement the precision of autoencoders. Unlike data-driven methods alone, our framework combines the computational efficiency of heuristic methods with the adaptability of deep learning models. This proof-of-concept demonstrates the feasibility of scalable and adaptive motion style transfer and lays the foundation for future generalization to more advanced techniques.

The contributions of this paper are as follows: (1) a novel hybrid framework for motion style transfer, (2) a demonstration of its effectiveness using benchmark datasets (XIA, 100Style, and SHS), and (3) insights into the complementary strengths of heuristic and data-driven techniques for achieving scalable, high-quality motion adaptation. The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 details the proposed methodology, blending heuristic and data-driven approaches. Section 3 presents experimental results and analysis. Section 4 explores challenges and future directions, and Section 5 concludes with key findings.

2 METHODOLOGY

This section introduces a hybrid framework for motion style transfer, combining heuristic techniques (Radial Basis Functions and phase features) with a data-driven autoencoder architecture. The novelty of this framework lies in its ability to integrate the computational efficiency of heuristic methods with the adaptability of deep learning models, enabling scalable and adaptive motion style transfer with minimal data dependency. Unlike traditional methods that rely solely on extensive datasets or predefined rules, our approach bridges these paradigms, offering precise control over motion style while maintaining computational efficiency. The proposed framework is illustrated in Figure 2, comprising an Autoencoder architecture enhanced with a control signal for dynamic motion style adaptation. The process begins with the Input Motion, which is pre-processed into motion features such as Radial Basis Function (RBF), Equation 1 and, phase-related information (Equation 2). These features are termed heuristic methods because they are derived from fixed mathematical formulations and domain-specific knowledge, rather than being learned from data.

Figure 2: Motion Style Transfer Framework: Input motion is processed into features and encoded into a latent space. A Control Signal modifies the latent representation to adjust motion style. The Decoder reconstructs the motion, optimized using the Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss to minimize differences with the input motion.

Figure 3: Physiotherapy motion capture session from the SHS dataset: Participants are performing rehabilitation exercises while wearing the Xsens motion capture system. This system captures full-body movements with high precision, providing data used for heuristic feature extraction and motion style transfer in this study.

For example, RBF provides localized motion variations by applying predefined basis functions, while phase features capture rhythmic and temporal changes using analytical representations. This integration ensures that the framework remains computationally efficient while delivering precise motion style variations. The control signal in our approach serves as a numerical parameter embedded in the latent space, enabling fine-grained modulation of motion characteristics. Motion style, as defined in our framework, refers to the spatiotemporal variations in motion dynamics that convey attributes such as speed, energy, or emotion. The control signal is not a static representation of a specific style but rather a flexible mechanism that allows adjustments to existing styles or the creation of new variations. For instance, the control signal can be applied as a continuous variable to subtly modify motion attributes, such as increasing the energy level of a neutral walk. This adaptability ensures that the control signal can either emulate predefined styles or explore interpolations and extrapolations in the style space, increasing diversity and utility. In the latent space, the control signal interacts with the encoded representation of motion, acting as a modifier that shifts the motion's underlying structure. By doing so, it provides a structured way to apply style transformations without retraining

Figure 4: The results of our method using Phase features for the SHS dataset and the control signal is 0.5. [All the plots correspond to the hip joint.]

Figure 5: The results of our method using Phase features for the XIA dataset (Angry walk) and the control signal is 1.5.[All the plots correspond to the hip joint.]

the model. This flexibility makes it a powerful tool for generating realistic and diverse motion styles from minimal input data.

$$\phi(x) = \alpha \exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (1)$$

Equation 1: Radial Basis Function (RBF) representation, where $\phi(x)$ represents the RBF value, α is the scaling factor (amplitude), μ is the center of the basis function, and σ^2 is the variance controlling the width.

The RBF data includes three key features: Alpha (amplitude), Mu (mean), and Sigma² (variance), which collectively define the shape and influence of the basis function on motion representation. Alpha determines the magnitude of motion variations, Mu shifts the motion to specific positions, and Sigma² controls the spread of the function, influencing the smoothness and precision of the motion.

In addition to RBF, we calculate phase-related features based on the work by Starke et al.[16]; these features include frequency,

Figure 6: The results of our method using Phase features for the 100Style dataset (Zombie walk) and the control signal is 1.5.[All the plots correspond to the hip joint.]

amplitude, offset, and the phase manifold and contribute to reconstructing motion styles. The frequency dictates the speed and periodicity of motion, amplitude controls the intensity or magnitude of movements, and the offset adjusts the baseline of the motion. Finally, the phase manifold captures cumulative temporal changes, preserving the overall flow and natural rhythm of motion. By combining these features, the reconstructed motion retains realistic style variations while enabling fine-tuned adjustments based on the input motion characteristics.

$$\Phi(t) = \left[\sin\left(\sum_{k=1}^K \theta_k(t)\right), \cos\left(\sum_{k=1}^K \theta_k(t)\right) \right] \quad (2)$$

Equation 2: Phase manifold representation, where $\theta_k(t)$ is the phase at time t for frequency k .

These features are fed into the Encoder, a neural network that extracts meaningful representations and compresses the input motion into a lower-dimensional Latent Space. In the latent space, a Control Signal is introduced to adjust specific characteristics of the motion, such as speed, energy, or intensity. This signal allows for flexible style manipulation without the need for retraining the model, enabling the generation of diverse motion styles from the same input motion. The modified latent representation is then passed through the Decoder, which reconstructs the motion data.

This reconstructed motion integrates the effects of the control signal, producing a stylized version of the input motion. The Loss Function, specifically the Mean Squared Error (MSE), measures the reconstruction accuracy by comparing the reconstructed motion with the original motion. This feedback is used during training to optimize the model parameters, ensuring that the output motion preserves the essential structure of the input while accommodating the applied control signal. This hybrid approach combines the strengths of data-driven autoencoders with heuristic control, achieving precise and efficient motion style adaptation.

3 RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The study utilized a workstation equipped with an Intel Core i7-8700K CPU and 16GB RAM for initial development and testing, while Google Colab was employed for additional computational resources, particularly for model training and evaluation. The experiments were conducted on three datasets: XIA [19], 100-Style [10],

Figure 7: The results of our method using RBF features for the SHS dataset and the control signal is 1.5.[All the plots correspond to the hip joint.]

and data we collected for an SHS project. The SHS dataset (Figure 3) which includes physiotherapy exercises performed by professional physiotherapists, provides high-quality motion capture data for various rehabilitation movements. The SHS dataset [12] consists of motion capture sequences with 6070 frames and a fine temporal resolution of 0.01 seconds per frame, enabling smooth and precise motion analysis. It includes 15 joints, featuring key segments such as Pelvis, LeftUpperLeg, LeftLowerLeg, and RightUpperLeg, which capture detailed skeletal movements. This dataset is particularly well-suited for applications like motion style transfer and biomechanical analysis due to its inclusion of high-resolution motion capture data from the Xsens system, which provides detailed skeletal movement information. The dataset’s diversity in motion styles and activities enables training and evaluation of models for style transfer, while its precise joint trajectories and biomechanical features facilitate accurate analysis of movement patterns and physical dynamics. During the preprocessing step, we employed PyMotion [18] to extract motion features.

The proposed method employs a 1D convolutional autoencoder for motion style transfer, optimized for efficiency and performance. The encoder uses three Conv1D layers with 128, 64, and 32 filters, a kernel size of 3, and strides of 1 and 2 to downsample the input. A Dense layer with 64 neurons compresses the features into the latent space. The decoder mirrors the encoder, upsampling the data with Conv1DTranspose layers and reconstructing it through a final Conv1D output layer with a linear activation. The model, optimized with Adam and MSE loss, is trained for 100 epochs with a batch size of 1, suitable for small, sequential motion datasets. Figures 4, 5, and 6 presents the results of our proposed method using Phase features, while Figures 7, 8, 9 illustrates the outcomes with RBF features. In both figures, the blue curve represents the original motion, the orange curve corresponds to the reconstructed motion

Figure 8: The results of our method using RBF features for the XIA (Angry Walk) dataset and the control signal is 1.5.[All the plots correspond to the hip joint.]

without applying the control signal, and the green curve shows the reconstructed motion after incorporating the control signal.

3.1 Key Findings

We summarize here some key findings from initial experiments, which we need to evaluate more thoroughly through quantitative and qualitative analysis.

- **Reconstruction Accuracy:** The reconstructed motion closely aligns with the original input across all evaluated features, demonstrating the model’s high precision.
- **Control Signal Impact:** The controlled motion effectively amplifies specific motion characteristics such as frequency components, baseline offsets, and amplitude peaks, showcasing the method’s adaptability as shown in Figure 12, 13.
- **Low Reconstruction Loss:** The Mean Squared Error (MSE) remains minimal across frames, validating the autoencoder’s ability to compress and reconstruct motion data with minimal information loss.
- **Comparison Between Phase and RBF Features:** While both methods achieve effective reconstruction, Phase features demonstrate smoother transitions over frames, making them ideal for capturing rhythmic and temporal changes. In contrast, the RBF features provide sharper and more localized variations, enabling finer control over motion intensity and amplitude. This comparison highlights the complementary strengths of Phase and RBF features for different aspects of motion style transfer.

Figure 9: The results of our method using RBF features for the 100style dataset(Zombie Walk) and the control signal is 1.5.[All the plots correspond to the hip joint.]

- **Different datasets, Different joints:**The results were very promising on different datasets with different skeletonizations and on all joints as illustrated in Figures 10,11 .

4 CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTION

The proposed hybrid framework, which combines heuristic and data-driven methods, demonstrates promising capabilities for achieving scalable and adaptive motion styles. However, several challenges remain to be addressed to further enhance its effectiveness. One critical limitation lies in the dependency on extensive datasets required by the data-driven components. While the integration of heuristic techniques such as RBF and phase features reduces reliance on large datasets, the diversity and representation of motion styles in the dataset still affect the model’s generalization and adaptability. Moreover, heuristic methods, despite their computational efficiency, are sensitive to parameter settings, such as frequency or variance, which can impact the realism and diversity of the reconstructed motion. Another key challenge is the seamless integration of control signals into the latent space, which is essential for achieving precise and fine-grained style modulation. Ensuring scalability and robustness of this integration while maintaining motion quality across diverse styles is a complex task.

Future work will focus on overcoming these limitations by employing advanced data augmentation techniques to expand the diversity of training datasets, enabling robust style transfer across a broader range of motions. Transfer learning and unsupervised learning will also be explored to reduce dependence on labeled data and improve adaptability in data-scarce scenarios. To enhance the control signal’s effectiveness, further optimization will aim at achieving real-time modulation of motion styles, making the system more responsive to dynamic environments. Human-in-the-loop (HITL) methodologies will be incorporated to allow interactive and

Figure 10: The results of our method using phase features for the SHS dataset and the control signal is 0.5.[All the plots correspond to the left-hand joint.]

Figure 11: The results of our method using phase features for the SHS dataset and the control signal is 0.5.[All the plots correspond to the right-leg joint.]

fine-grained control over motion styles, striking a balance between heuristic precision and data-driven flexibility.

Additionally, extending the framework to support multi-character interactions and crowd-level dynamics represents a significant opportunity for future research. Addressing these challenges will enable the framework to handle synchronized and large-scale motion style transfer, paving the way for applications in collaborative robotics, immersive virtual environments, and large-scale simulations. These advancements will solidify the hybrid approach as a scalable and adaptive solution for motion style transfer in diverse and complex scenarios.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced a hybrid framework for motion style transfer that combines the precision of data-driven autoencoder models with the efficiency of heuristic methods, such as RBF and phase features. This approach addresses key challenges in the field by reducing dependency on large datasets while achieving high-quality, adaptive motion styles. By incorporating a control signal into the latent space, the framework enables real-time, fine-grained

Figure 12: Results of Our Methods on the SHS Dataset using phase features: Demonstrating the impact of control signals on motion speed. A control signal of 0.5 decreases the motion speed, while a control signal of 1.5 increases it, showcasing the adaptability and precision of our approach.

Figure 13: The SHS health scenario depicted in Figure 12 illustrates variations based on the original BVH (left), generating a slower style (middle) and a faster style (right).

adjustments to motion characteristics, making it suitable for applications in gaming, virtual reality, and robotics. Experimental results demonstrate the method's effectiveness in generating realistic and diverse motion styles, paving the way for scalable and interactive motion adaptation solutions. Future work will explore enhancing the framework's robustness and extending it to multi-character interactions and crowd dynamics.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Abdul-Massih, I. Yoo, and B. Benes. Motion style retargeting to characters with different morphologies. In *Computer Graphics Forum*,

- vol. 36, pp. 86–99. Wiley Online Library, 2017. 1
- [2] K. Aberman, Y. Weng, D. Lischinski, D. Cohen-Or, and B. Chen. Unpaired motion style transfer from video to animation. *ACM Transactions on Graphics (TOG)*, 39(4):64–1, 2020. 2
- [3] S. A. Etemad and A. Arya. Expert-driven perceptual features for modeling style and affect in human motion. *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems*, 46(4):534–545, 2016. 2
- [4] D. Holden, I. Habibie, I. Kusajima, and T. Komura. Fast neural style transfer for motion data. *IEEE computer graphics and applications*, 37(4):42–49, 2017. 2
- [5] E. Hsu, K. Pulli, and J. Popović. Style translation for human motion. *ACM Trans. Graph.*, 24(3):1082–1089, July 2005. doi: 10.1145/1073204.1073315 2
- [6] D.-K. Jang, S. Park, and S.-H. Lee. Motion puzzle: Arbitrary motion style transfer by body part. *ACM Transactions on Graphics (TOG)*, 41(3):1–16, 2022. 2
- [7] K. Kritsis, A. Gkiokas, A. Pikrakis, and V. Katsouras. Danceconv: Dance motion generation with convolutional networks. *IEEE Access*, 10:44982–45000, 2022. 2
- [8] P. Li, K. Aberman, Z. Zhang, R. Hanocka, and O. Sorkine-Hornung. Ganimator: Neural motion synthesis from a single sequence. *ACM Transactions on Graphics (TOG)*, 41(4):1–12, 2022. 2
- [9] W. Ma, S. Xia, J. K. Hodgins, X. Yang, C. Li, and Z. Wang. Modeling style and variation in human motion. In *Proceedings of the 2010 ACM SIGGRAPH/Eurographics Symposium on Computer Animation*, pp. 21–30, 2010. 1
- [10] I. Mason, S. Starke, and T. Komura. Real-time style modelling of human locomotion via feature-wise transformations and local motion phases. *Proceedings of the ACM on Computer Graphics and Interactive Techniques*, 5(1), may 2022. doi: 10.1145/3522618 3
- [11] J. Pan, H. Sun, and Y. Kong. Fast human motion transfer based on a meta network. *Information sciences*, 547:367–383, 2021. 1
- [12] S. Project. Sharespace embodied social experiences in hybrid shared spaces. <https://sharespace.eu/>, 2024. Accessed: 2024-06-07. 4
- [13] C. Rose, M. F. Cohen, and B. Bodenheimer. Verbs and adverbs: Multidimensional motion interpolation. *IEEE Computer Graphics and Applications*, 18(5):32–40, 1998. 1
- [14] H. J. Smith, C. Cao, M. Neff, and Y. Wang. Efficient neural networks for real-time motion style transfer. *Proc. ACM Comput. Graph. Interact. Tech.*, 2(2), July 2019. doi: 10.1145/3340254 2
- [15] W. Song, X. Jin, S. Li, C. Chen, A. Hao, X. Hou, N. Li, and H. Qin. Arbitrary motion style transfer with multi-condition motion latent diffusion model. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pp. 821–830, 2024. 2
- [16] S. Starke, I. Mason, and T. Komura. Deepphase: Periodic autoencoders for learning motion phase manifolds. *ACM Transactions on Graphics (TOG)*, 41(4):1–13, 2022. 2, 3
- [17] T. Tao, X. Zhan, Z. Chen, and M. van de Panne. Style-erd: Responsive and coherent online motion style transfer. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pp. 6593–6603, June 2022. 2
- [18] UPC-ViRVIG. Pymotion: Motion processing library. <https://github.com/UPC-ViRVIG/pymotion>, 2024. Accessed: 2024-06-07. 4
- [19] S. Xia, C. Wang, J. Chai, and J. Hodgins. Realtime style transfer for unlabeled heterogeneous human motion. *ACM Transactions on Graphics (TOG)*, 34(4):1–10, 2015. 3